

IMPROVEMENT OF THE PROCEDURE FOR COLLECTING THE UTILIZATION FEE FOR IMPORTED HYBRID AND ELECTRIC VEHICLES

Kaljanov B.D.

Senior Inspector at the Centralized "MED" Customs Post, Tashkent City Customs Department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14274782>

Abstract. *This article provides information about the customs duties and utilization fees for hybrid and electric vehicles imported into the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years. It analyzes the types of customs duties and utilization fees granted as exemptions, as well as the types of hybrid and electric vehicles for which utilization fees are being collected. The article suggests optimization of the utilization fees applicable to these vehicles, identifies current issues in the practice of fee collection, and provides practical recommendations for solving these problems. Moreover, the article extensively discusses the types of engines used in hybrid and electric vehicles, their classification under the respective HS Codes, and offers scientific suggestions and practical recommendations on the topic.*

Keywords: *import, utilization fee, customs duties, exemptions, HS Code, hybrid, plug-in hybrid, electric vehicle.*

The correct implementation of customs policy in foreign economic activity plays a crucial role in creating a favorable investment environment. It ensures the effective integration of the country's economy into the global economic system, while also contributing to economic and ecological security. The policy helps protect the environment and public health from the harmful effects of vehicle operation, boosts budget revenues through economic measures, and ensures economic security by supporting domestic producers.

In recent years, the share of vehicles in foreign trade turnover has significantly increased. Due to rising demand for vehicles in the domestic market, it is essential to correctly identify vehicle categories, classes, and HS Codes (HSN) when processing vehicles through customs. Customs officials are required to have the necessary knowledge and skills to accurately calculate customs duties and utilization fees based on these categories and rates.

According to the International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA), which Uzbekistan has been a full member of since 1998, in 2022, Uzbekistan produced more than 333,000 vehicles. This ranked Uzbekistan 28th in the global automotive production ranking, 2nd among the CIS countries after Russia, and 1st among Central Asian countries (see Figure 1).

In addition, the adoption of relevant regulations supporting the transport-logistics and tourism sectors, along with customs exemptions for entrepreneurs on the import of vehicles, has contributed to the growth of imports in this category of goods.

When examining the imports of vehicles categorized by class from 2021 to 2023, we can observe a significant increase in the volume of light vehicle imports. In fact, the official registration volume of light vehicles has nearly quadrupled, making it a leading category in terms of imports. Additionally, we can also see an increase in the import volume of trailers and semitrailers during the same period (see Figure 2).

This growth highlights the expanding demand for vehicles in the domestic market and underscores the importance of streamlining customs procedures and ensuring proper classification of vehicle types to effectively manage imports and related duties.

Транспорт воситаларини ишлаб чиқариш бўйича жаҳон рейтингги 2022 йилда (минг дона)			
Ўрин	Давлат	Сони	
1	Хитой	27 020,6	
2	АҚШ	10 060,3	
3	Япония	7 835,5	
4	Ҳиндистон	5 456,9	
5	Корея	3 757,0	
6	Германия	3 677,8	
7	Мексика	3 509,1	
8	Бразилия	2 369,8	
9	Испания	2 219,5	
21	Россия	608,1	
28	Ўзбекистон	333,6	
45	Озарбайжон	2,0	
47	Украина	1,5	
Жаҳон		85 016,7	

Figure 1: Global Ranking of Vehicle Production in 2022

Figure 2: Import Statistics of Types of Machinery and Vehicles (in Million USD)

In the strategy for Uzbekistan's transition to a "green" economy from 2019 to 2030, the production and expansion of the use of vehicles that meet Euro-4 and higher standards, with improved energy efficiency and environmental specifications, including electric vehicles, hybrid engine vehicles, and vehicles running on gas fuel, has been emphasized. Based on the directives of this strategy, the study will focus on the import volumes of hybrid and electric vehicles (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Statistical Value of Hybrid and Electric Vehicle Imports (in million dollars).

In our country, the introduction of a utilization fee for certain goods has been implemented as an economic measure to encourage the transition to a "green" economy and ensure environmental protection.

The utilization fee is paid to protect ecological safety, citizens' health, and the environment from the harmful effects of waste generated after the consumption characteristics of wheeled vehicles, self-propelled machines, their trailers, pneumatic rubber tires, and tires are lost.

According to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 28, 2022, "On the Introduction of the 2022 Edition of the Foreign Economic Activity Commodity Nomenclature of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (PR-460), the 2022 edition of the Foreign Economic Activity Commodity Nomenclature (hereinafter referred to as TIF TN) was implemented starting from January 1, 2023.

In the explanation for the TIF TN position 8703 (passenger cars), the following clarifications are provided for hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles:

(HEV) Hybrid Electric Vehicles are those that combine an internal combustion engine (ICE) with one or more electric motors. These vehicles use both fuel and electrical energy stored in a system (e.g., battery, capacitor, flywheel/generator) for mechanical movement.

(PHEV) Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles are vehicles that can recharge their electric batteries from an electric socket or charging station (generator), making them capable of both electric and internal combustion engine operation.

(EV) Electric Vehicles are vehicles powered by one or more electric motors, which are operated by a battery.

Due to the classification of electric vehicles in the TIF TN 8703 80 subposition, both plug-in hybrids and fully electric vehicles (EVs) are categorized as electric vehicles.

The reason for classifying plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV) as a type of hybrid vehicle is that, although they have an internal combustion engine (ICE), the engine does not directly drive the wheels. Instead, it generates electricity to charge the electric motor's battery, and then the electric motor drives the wheels.

In this configuration, the ICE operates at an optimal speed to continuously generate the necessary amount of electricity, which is then used to power the electric motor and charge the batteries (Figure 4).

4-figure: Energy sources and CIF TN codes of hybrid and electric vehicles.

Hybrid – The internal combustion engine (ICE) and electric motor work simultaneously to provide maximum power or are used separately to ensure more efficient fuel consumption.

In hybrid vehicles, the ICE can directly move the vehicle and charge the battery that powers the electric motor. The electric motor provides additional power and fuel efficiency, and can operate either on its own or in combination with the ICE.

These types of light vehicles are classified under the TIF TN codes 8703 40, 8703 50, 8703 60, or 8703 70.

Examples of plug-in hybrid vehicles currently being imported include “Li One”, “Li L6”, “Li L7”, “Li L8”, “Li L9”, “Voyah Free”, “Changan Deepal”, “Fengon S508”, “Leapmotor C10”, “Leapmotor C11”, “Yangwang U8”, and “Leapmotor C16”. Given that these vehicles have internal combustion engines, and the customs duties and utilization fee rates for their TIF TN codes 8703 60 or 8703 80 vary, there is a need for a clear classification decision. Importing them from the People's Republic of China requires studying each model individually and conducting necessary inspections, which, in turn, delays the customs clearance process and may lead to legitimate objections from TIF participants.

Although plug-in hybrid vehicles, like hybrid vehicles, are equipped with internal combustion engines, their TIF TN code is classified under subheading 8703 80, the same as electric vehicles. Therefore, when clearing for the "free circulation" (import) customs regime, hybrid vehicles have a customs duty of 15%, while plug-in hybrid vehicles are subject to a zero percent duty. The utilization fee is set at 120 times the base calculation amount (BCA) for hybrid vehicles, while for plug-in hybrids, it is 30 times the BCA (Figure 5).

Асосий тўлов турлари	Гибрид энгил автомобилларга божхона тўловлари ва утилизация йиғимидан ставкалари	Электромобилларга ёки изчил-гибрид автомобилларга божхона тўловлари ва утилизация йиғимидан ставкалари
Импорт божхона божи*	15%	0%
ККС**	12%	12%
Утилизация йиғими	120 БХМ***	30 БХМ***
* - Импорт божхона божи божхона қийматиغا нисбатан		
** - Қўшилган қиймат солиғи божхона қиймати ва импорт божхона божи тўламиниң йиғиндисига нисбатан		
*** - Базавий ҳисоблаш миқдорига нисбатан		

Figure 5. Customs Duties and Utilization Fee Rates for Hybrid and Electric Vehicles

Taking into account the factors mentioned in the previous analysis, we can now compare the advantages of hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles relative to each other.

Advantages of Plug-in Hybrid Vehicles over Electric Vehicles:

Longer distance coverage with full energy (electricity + fuel);

The ability to use both types of refueling (electricity and fuel);

Adaptability to various weather conditions;

Greater power due to the combination of two engines.

Advantages of Plug-in Hybrid Vehicles over Hybrid Vehicles:

More competitive in the domestic market due to lower customs duties and utilization fees;

Lower fuel consumption and related costs due to the longer distance covered by the electric motor;

No requirement to present an environmental certificate during customs clearance.

Statistical Analysis of the Value of Hybrid, Plug-in Hybrid, and Electric Vehicles Imported into Uzbekistan: The study of the statistical value of imported hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles into Uzbekistan led to a series of conclusions. Specifically:

The volume of hybrid vehicles reached USD 316.2 billion in 2023 (compared to USD 4.4 billion in 2021), a 71.45-fold increase;

The volume of plug-in hybrid vehicles amounted to USD 91.8 billion in 2023 (compared to USD 0.1 billion in 2021), an 850.53-fold increase;

The volume of electric vehicles reached USD 608.6 billion in 2023 (compared to USD 33.6 billion in 2021), an 18.11-fold increase, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Ratio of Statistical Value of Imported Hybrid, Plug-in Hybrid, and Electric Vehicles from 2021 to 2023

By years	By types of vehicles (in thousand USD)		
	Hybrid	Plug-in hybrid	electric vehicle
2021 year	4 425,67	107,99	33 606,94
2022 year	7 039,70	5 215,33	132 066,23
2023 year	316 226,84	91 844,51	608 617,54
"Difference (times)"	71,45	850,53	18,11

The analysis above indicates that the advantages of plug-in hybrid vehicles (PHEVs) over hybrid and electric vehicles, along with the high demand for these vehicles in the domestic market, have led to a noticeable increase in their import in recent years. During this period, a total of 2,810 plug-in hybrid vehicles were imported, and an environmental fee of 27.8 billion UZS was collected. Given that these vehicles are equipped with an internal combustion engine (ICE) and considering their higher environmental impact compared to electric vehicles, if the utilization fee rate had been set at 90 BHM instead of 30 BHM, an additional 55.6 billion UZS could have been collected.

Furthermore, based on the factors discussed above, if the import customs duty had been set at 5%, a customs duty of 213.7 billion UZS could have been collected for these vehicles.

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 347 of June 2, 2020, "On the Introduction of Utilization Fees for Certain Types of Goods," the

utilization fee rates for light vehicles are set based on the engine size, with the same rate applied to both hybrid and electric vehicles. Interestingly, the same rate is applied to both plug-in hybrid and electric vehicles, as shown in Figure 6.

III. M1 тоифали транспорт воситалари, шу жумладан юқори ўтувчан 9 тоифали транспорт воситалари: енгил автомобиллар			
Транспорт воситалари двигателнинг иш ҳажми билан:	ТИФ ТН коди	ишлаб чиқарилган мuddатидан бошлаб 3 йилдан ортиқ бўлмаган	ишлаб чиқарилган мuddатидан бошлаб 3 йилдан ортиқ бўлган
1 000 см.куб гача	8703	30	90
1 000 см.куб дан 2 000 см.куб гача	8703 80 000 лардан ташқари	120	210
2 000 см.куб дан 3 000 см.куб гача		180	330
3 000 см.куб дан 3 500 см.куб гача		180	390
3 500 см.куб дан ортиқ		300	480
Қор орқали ҳаракатланиш учун махсус мўлжалланган транспорт воситалари; голфчиларни ташиш учун автомобиллар ва шу каби транспорт воситалари	8703 10	30	90
Электродвигателга эга бўлган транспорт воситалари, гибрид қувватли транспорт воситалари бундан мустасно	8703 80 000	30	90

Figure 6. Utilization Fee Rates for Light Vehicles

In the import of hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles, the utilization fee accounted for 10.5% of customs duties in 2021, amounting to 18.1 billion UZS. In 2022, this fee increased to 8.5%, reaching 47.5 billion UZS, and in 2023, it represented 10.1%, totaling 331.5 billion UZS (Table 2).

Table 2. Percentage of Utilization Fee in Customs Duties for 2021–2023 (in million UZS)

By years	Tax fees	Utilization fee	utilization fee's share in customs duties (in percentage)
2021	172312,98	18066,09	10,5%
2022	557794,72	47581,20	8,5%
2023	3284402,90	331589,10	10,1%
Total	4014510,60	397236,39	9,9%

Based on the analysis and scientific research conducted on the practice of collecting the utilization fee for hybrid and electric vehicle imports, the following conclusions were made:

Due to the different energy sources used for movement in hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles, and the varying customs duties and utilization fee rates for their corresponding TIF TN codes, it was suggested that these rates should be optimized for these vehicles.

Taking into account the differences in the impact of imported hybrid, plug-in hybrid, and electric vehicles on the environment and public health, it is proposed that the utilization fee for hybrid vehicles should be set lower (40% less than the current rate) compared to internal combustion engine vehicles, while the utilization fee for plug-in hybrid vehicles should be higher than that for electric vehicles (100% more than the current rate).

While the TIF TN code "8703 80" should remain unchanged, its description should be adjusted to "vehicles powered only by electric motors or generators", and it is considered appropriate to introduce a 5% customs duty on plug-in hybrid vehicles.

The implementation of these proposals would, without causing any inconvenience to business entities, align with the rules of the "green" economy, encouraging the import of light

vehicles, including hybrids, plug-in hybrids, and electric vehicles. This will promote the efficient collection of customs duties and utilization fees, contributing to an increase in government revenue through higher import volumes.

REFERENCES

1. Global Automotive Industry: Numbers, History, Rankings. <https://dknews.kz/ru/dk-avto/314126-mirovoy-avtoprom-cifry-istoriya-reytingi>
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ПҚ-4477, dated 04.10.2019, "Approval of the Strategy for Transition to a 'Green' Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2030". <https://lex.uz/docs/4539502>
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ПҚ-4477, dated 04.10.2019, "Approval of the Strategy for Transition to a 'Green' Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2030". <https://lex.uz/docs/4539502>
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 362-II, dated 05.04.2002, "On Waste". <https://lex.uz/docs/42423?ONDATE=01.01.2024>
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ПҚ-460, dated 28.12.2022, "Implementation of the 2022 Revision of the Nomenclature of Goods for Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan". <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6330249>
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ПҚ-3818, dated 29.06.2018, "Measures to Further Regulate Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Improve the Customs and Tariff Regulation System". <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6330249>
7. Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 347, dated 02.06.2020, "On the Introduction of a Utilization Fee for Certain Types of Goods". <https://lex.uz/docs/4844263>
8. Economic Commission for Europe, Committee on Inland Transport, World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations, Consolidated Resolution on Vehicle Construction (R.3). <https://unece.org/DAM/trans/main/wp29/wp29resolutions/ECE-TRANS-WP.29-78r6r.pdf>